

observations were used to develop the model for LsA. The remaining 330 observations were used to validate the generated model.

Multiple regression analysis indicated a significant exponential relationship between LnA and LsA (Fig. 1). This relationship is described in the mathematical model as

$$LsA = \exp(1.545387 + 0.900306 (\ln LnA))$$

where LsA is lesion size in $\text{mm}^2 \text{cm}^{-2}$ leaf area, ln is the natural logarithm with base e ($e = 2.718$), and LnA is lesion number cm^{-2} leaf area. The model fits the disease observations reasonably well with a coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.85. Both the β_0 (y-intercept) and β_1 (slope coefficient) coefficient terms have significant contributions to the model with t-values of 105.4 and 86.7, respectively. To test the validity of the model, the closeness in the values of LsA in the validation set and that of the model-predicted LsA was determined.

Three criteria were used to determine such closeness: the variance (VAR_{diff}) of the difference between observed and predicted values (prediction error) is less than the mean square error (MSE) from the regression analysis of the full data set ($n=1,318$), average prediction error (APE)

1. Relationship between lesion number and lesion size in leaf blast.

is close to zero, and the β_0 and β_1 obtained from regressing actual and predicted LsA is not significantly different from zero and unity, respectively.

A 1:1 relationship between observed and predicted LsA for the validation data set ($n = 330$) was revealed (Fig. 2). The VAR_{diff} (0.2704) was less than the MSE (0.2856) of the full data set and the APE was 0.0025, which is near zero value. Likewise, both β_0 and β_1 terms satisfy the third criterion,

2. Linear relationship of predicted and observed lesion size.

suggesting that the model presented could be used to accurately estimate the LsA on the basis of LnA from new blast data sets. These data sets would likely come from various blast studies, specifically cultivar resistance screening, compatibility and virulence spectrum studies, and validation experiments for simulation models.

These results apply to sporulating blast lesions. ■

A simple method for estimating yield loss of rice due to severe panicle blast

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We investigated the relationship between panicle blast severity and yield loss of rice. We showed that yield loss can be estimated using a simple method under severe panicle blast situations.

We used Mineasahi, a Japanese rice cultivar with a low level of partial resistance to blast, and near-isogenic lines (NILs) with different complete resistance genes to blast. These NILs were developed from Japanese rice cultivars Sasanishiki and Nipponbare.

Seedlings were transplanted at 15- × 30-cm spacing in 5.8- m^2 plots during 1992-94.

Blast developed in the plots from natural infection. To obtain different levels of panicle blast severity, several fungicides were applied to Mineasahi, and mixed or

single plantings of NILs with different resistances to blast were made. Panicle blast severity was assessed by the Asaga scale (see table) on 20 representative hills in each plot about 1 mo after heading. The mean of the assessed values was transformed to a

Asaga scale for assessing panicle blast severity in ricefields.

Grade	Description	Diseased spikelets ^a (%)
0	No panicle blast observed.	0
1	A few panicle branches diseased (slight). Diseased panicle branches are seen at a glance and neck blast is found in some cases (moderate).	5 10
3	Many panicle branches are diseased and neck blast is observed (a lot).	25
4	Many panicle branches are diseased and diseased neck nodes are moderate (severe).	50
5	Panicle branches and neck nodes are severely diseased (very severe).	75
6	All panicles are diseased.	100

^aDiseased spikelets include the spikelets prematurely killed by infection of *P. grisea* on neck nodes, panicle branches, and spikelet pedicels.

Relationship between yield loss (%) and spikelets diseased with panicle blast (%).

percentage of diseased spikelets with the Asaga scale (see table).

In each plot, 80 hills were harvested to determine grain yield for Mineasahi and rough rice yield for the NILs. Yield loss due to panicle blast was calculated each year from an estimated yield with no

panicle blast for each of Mineasahi and the NILs. The estimated yield with no panicle blast was determined by extrapolating the regression line of yield and percentage of spikelets diseased with panicle blast to the percentage of spikelets diseased with panicle blast with a value of zero.

In each experiment, yield loss was correlated positively with the percentage of spikelets diseased with panicle blast (significant at $P < 0.01$) and the yield loss almost agreed with the percentage of diseased spikelets. However, the agreement between panicle blast and the diseased spikelet percentage and yield loss was not severe compared with the other experiments (see figure).

Yield loss caused by panicle blast varied with the time of *P. grisea* infection on rice panicles and was affected by leaf blast severity. Moreover, weather conditions and cultivar resistance may affect yield loss. However, our results show that yield loss due to panicle blast can be estimated by the percentage of diseased spikelets under severe disease conditions. The method is very simple and the percentage of diseased spikelets in rice hills can also be assessed directly without the Asaga scale. Farmers who cultivate rice under severe panicle blast conditions can use the method to estimate yield losses due to the disease. ■

Inoculation method for rice bunt

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Incidence of rice bunt (kernel smut) caused by *Neovossia horrida* (Tak.) Padwick and Khan is erratic, so screening germplasm for bunt or chemicals for use against bunt under natural incidence is not reliable.

We studied the effect of inoculation method and crop stage on bunt development in a glasshouse in 1993 and 1994. Twenty-five tillers in three replications were inoculated at five growth stages (booting, panicle exertion, anthesis, milk grain, and dough grain). Uninoculated panicles served as the check.

Effect of inoculation method at different stages of growth on rice bunt infection.

Growth stage/method	Bunted grains (%)	
	1993	1994
Boot - syringe	12.00	12.33
	(20.26) ^a	(20.56)
syringe	3.00	3.66
	(9.95)	(11.02)
Panicle exertion - spray	6.67	6.67
	(14.95)	(14.95)
Anthesis - spray	4.00	4.33
	(11.52)	(12.00)
Milk - spray	0.00	0.00
	(0.00)	(0.00)
Dough - spray	0.00	0.00
	(0.00)	(0.00)
Uninoculated check	0.00	0.00
	(0.00)	(0.00)
CD (P = 0.05)	1.10	0.97
CV (%)	7.78	6.63

^a Figures in parentheses are angular transformed values.

Two inoculation methods were used. In the syringe method, 2 ml of sporidial suspension (2500 sporidia ml^{-1}) was injected into the boot. In the spray method, inoculum was sprayed on the panicles. The area enclosing the inoculated plants was covered with muslin cloth; water was sprinkled over the cloth to provide humidity.

At booting, half of the plants were inoculated by syringe method and the other half by spray method. At the other stages, the spray method was used.

The syringe inoculation method resulted in four times more bunted grains than did the spray method (see table). The best stage at which to spray using the spray method was panicle exertion, at which time maximum disease occurrence was recorded. No disease developed when the crop was inoculated after anthesis.

The syringe inoculation method should be adopted for screening germplasm, and the spray method should be used for evaluating antifungal compounds. The syringe inoculation method may not be feasible for inoculating crops on a large scale. ■